

THE ACTUAL STATUS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, opinions on the formation of acmeological positions of future teachers in higher education institutions, to increase their activity in the educational process, to awaken a sense of responsibility for their chosen profession, and to develop various reforms in society.

Key words and phrases: socio-economic, independent education, modern outlook, social necessity, digital economy, acmeological position, innovative and digital, market economy, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

In the scientific research carried out in the world and national education system on the improvement of the qualifications of educational staff, special attention is paid to the high professional potential of future pedagogic personnel, in which the main emphasis is on improving the acmeological competence of specialists in their profession, social scientific research aimed at forecasting the scope of general cultural competences of managers and pedagogues is being carried out based on expanding their activity through intellectual information systems (e-learning concept), CIVIC international evaluation program (citizenship, political literacy, patriotism, management level development). In this innovative direction, increasing the scope of competences of future pedagogues, improving the mechanisms for the development of universal competences of personnel, and training high-potential, flexible and competitive specialists, is one of the urgent issues for the educational system based on the equilibration of integration processes. Such a social phenomenon has gained particular relevance, and in the course of training, in the course of these studies, it is necessary to study the theoretical and methodological foundations of didactic, prognostic, personal, special, acmeological, general cultural and professional competencies of pedagogues, to improve them based on modern requirements, and to improve the quality and efficiency of education. It is important to develop proposals that scientifically justify the quality of education, to improve the quality assessment system of professional development education. In this regard, the topic of the dissertation dedicated to the study of these issues is relevant. [1:19-24]

One of the modern trends is to ensure the quality and competitiveness of educational institutions by developing the competence of specialists in the world. In the context of the "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" and "European Higher Education Area" (EHEA) concepts adopted at the 70th anniversary session of the UN General Assembly, the model of "competency-based learning" was introduced in personnel training and professional development. improvement of the mechanisms of continuous development of professional skills based on the humanization of education" was defined as one of the strategic directions. This ensures the integration of advanced foreign experiences of development of general cultural competencies of future pedagogues into the management and educational process along with professional competencies.[2:114-118]

Determining the prospects for the development of the new Uzbekistan, implementing large-scale reforms in order to take a worthy place among the countries of the developed world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements. Taking into account modern requirements, organization of regular improvement of cognitive competence development in future teachers is one of the urgent tasks of today.[3:28]

Materials and Methods:

Several variants of the teacher's professionogram are described in the literature (A.K. Markova, V.A. Slastenin, L.F. Spirin, etc.). The professional profile of the teacher reveals the features of successful implementation of professional activity, the requirements for achieving a socially acceptable result. Acmeogram reveals ways to raise the teacher's professional skills to higher levels. Therefore, the acmeogram can include the tasks of improving the teacher's qualifications. For example, mastering new teaching methods, developing one's individual style, etc.[4]

The creative side of the acmeological activity expressed in the development of the creativity and creative potential of the future teacher, as well as the manifestation and implementation of the future teacher's personality in the process of learning, is of particular importance. The design of his personal and professional development, the search for the most effective coordination that leads to the optimal achievement of professional "acme", as well as the formation of the individual activity style of the future teacher are personal characteristics expressed by the requirements of pedagogical activity.

The following personal qualities are necessary for the future teacher to carry out his professional activity: creativity, technical thinking, confidence in his own strength, constantly improving his professional skills, being able to manage processes with emotional-firmness, the results of the emergence of professional competence are among them.

Creative activity is a creative process that requires long-term preparation, erudition, and skills.

Creative activity is the basis of a person's long career, the source of all material and spiritual wealth.

Results

The level of formation of the main elements of human creativity and creative thinking has a great impact on the development of professional competence of future teachers and increases the productivity of teaching activities.

Designing the educational process as a professional activity of a pedagogue can be mastered by students - future teachers of vocational education during their professional pedagogical training.

In order to implement professional-pedagogical creativity competence, psychological-pedagogical conditions should be created. On the basis of the classification of professional-pedagogical creative activity, the creation of pedagogical conditions can be based on the structural components of personal activity: cognitive, creative, communicative, artistic activities. Accordingly, five different psychological states can be distinguished:

1. Knowing the essence, principles and processes of designing a unique style of pedagogical activity and the process of developing professional-pedagogical creativity.
2. Emotional and valuable attitude to professional pedagogical activity, to make sure of the need to effectively organize the educational process in higher education institutions.
3. The ability to creatively implement the educational process in higher education institutions aimed at the development of professional and pedagogical creativity.
4. In the course of collective activity, establishing relationships with other people focused on mutual communicative competence.
5. The need and ability to rationalize and harmonize the project of the educational process aimed at the development of professional and pedagogical creativity.[5]

The following general methodological principles are important for acmeology: determinism and social determination of the individual, development and humanism.

The principle of determinism reveals the specific features of the subject of acmeology - the way personal neoplasms appear, and at the same time, the social need for these qualities.

According to the principle of psychological determinism, external conditions determine the essence of an object and the result of its impact not strictly and unambiguously, but by breaking through internal conditions. Internal conditions are characterized by activity, specificity and selectivity.

The principle of psychological determinism has a clear acmeological content. Determining the internal conditions that promote self-development, the determinants of this development, is an important component of any acmeological research.

The uniqueness of the principle of determinism in acmeology is manifested in several ways:

First, acmeology considers the internal conditions of a person as motivating causes and determinants of development.

Secondly, the driving force of development is the individual, and the mechanism is self-regulation, self-organization.

Third, the process of personal development has a dual definition: internal and external. A decisive role in this is played by internal determination, the release of internal driving forces, and the determination of human capabilities. External acmeological influence turns out to be constructive only because it is focused on the person as a subject, that is, based on the recognition of the decisive role of internal mechanisms and conditions.

In acmeology, the principle of development means the subjective, valuable, ascending nature of development through the resolution of contradictions.

The application of the principle of development in acmeology includes:

to understand development as improvement, perfection, wholeness, optimal high level; "ascension movements" (according to S.L. Rubinstein);

recognition of the subjective nature of development;

implementation of development (and its analysis) through contradictions resolved by the subject;

taking into account the individual nature of development;

Establishing a connection between a person's life development and profession;

taking into account the potential and actual ratio in the development of a person; reveal its hidden, unrealized potential;

▣ determining the current stage of development in comparison with the ideal, perspective.

For acmeology, the essence of development is embodied in a personal quality, like culture.

In acmeology, the principle of humanism is aimed at human self-esteem, self-improvement, self-awareness, and the harmonization of relations in the process of development.

The principle of humanism offers three options for human support:

recognition of one's quality as a subject and the ability to independently resolve life conflicts;

"emancipation", actualization of his intellectual abilities, consciousness as ways, having them allows a person to optimally resolve conflicts;

simulating situations that rise to a new level of opening up one's possibilities for a person.

The task of acmeology in all three directions is not to develop a person only to the extent required by society or labor (as a labor force) or to the extent that he establishes himself. The humanistic task of acmeology is to promote the authenticity of human life, the completeness of its self-realization.

Discussion

In acmeological studies, special methodological principles of acmeology are based and described. The principle of the topic of activity connects general and professional acmeology.

In acmeology, a person is considered in his state of activity. Acting, personality as a system "fits" (B.G. Ananyev) to other systems - life, activity, communication, knowledge in general. Therefore, a person's activity should be carried out in accordance with the quality and criteria of each of the established systems.

The activity presented by the society to its performer, the quality of the subject appears as a new, changed quality of the person, which means not only the matching of abilities, goals and his needs, but also a complete reconstruction of the entire system of his mental organization.

The subject of activity finds the ratio of external and internal determinations, necessity and freedom, regulation, standardization, standardization and individualization. The task of the subject is to resolve this contradiction in the current activity and in the entire active professional life of a person.

Based on the principle of the subject of activity, acmeology, on the one hand, reveals the most complete and satisfactory ways of self-expression in various spheres of life, which is a prerequisite for creativity. On the other hand, this principle allows to ensure the highest social and professional efficiency of representatives of various specialties.

The principle of the subject of life and activity is historically, theoretically and logically clear and fundamental to acmeology.

Life activity is defined as the sum of all types of social activities, behaviors and relationships of a certain subject. S. L. Rubinstein, considering the person as an integral being that is formed, manifested and developed in the activity, emphasized that the person is not only a subject of activity, but even more widely - a subject of life. As a subject of life activity, a person always enters into a system of relations, which is significantly different in its breadth, intensity and level from the system of relations within any activity. Thus, life activity is the richest source of personal experience for any person, and acts as its context in relation to any field of activity.

For acmeology, the principle of the subject of life and activity means that a person "masters" his life conditions, creates secondary life conditions by building special life supports, life relationships and positions.[6:118]

In acmeology, a person's professional activity and self-determination of his life, self-development and formation of creativity, his life activity as a subject are considered. The main task of acmeology is the knowledge, practical skills, qualifications that depend on the person, who is a subject of conscious activity, to fully reveal and demonstrate his creative potential in various activity processes, in particular, within the framework of his chosen profession and specialty. , is to provide technologies.

V. Karimova "every period of development has its own significant aspect, the science of acmeology has appeared in recent years, which studies the conditions and factors of reaching maturity, from the point of view of the period, it studies the characteristics of the age periods under discussion. ", he says. Therefore, it is possible to predict the acmeological development of a person with different dynamic characteristics in each age period.

Innovative processes in informational education occur with the application of advanced foreign experiences and modern pedagogical approaches to the educational process. The era of traditional approaches in informed communication education has passed. Increasing the vital importance of education, using it as a means of forming students' worldview, critical and

creative thinking skills, understanding information and drawing vital conclusions from it is one of the urgent tasks of education for the development of acmeological competence today. Working with the informational text, understanding the vital truths in its essence, forming the ability to draw conclusions are the problems of modern methodology. This increases students' adaptability to real-life situations. Modern education is of great importance in forming students' ability to express their worldview. These requirements are in line with the requirements of the international assessment programs of modern education (PISA — Program for International Student Assessment), and the organization of classes based on modern pedagogical approaches is the growth indicator of the public education system of our country in the ranking of the world countries. provides achievement.

Conclusion

Education of future pedagogues in the conditions of informatization of education depends on multifaceted factors, it is a process based on the principle of development, which takes place in harmony with many tools and complex technologies. Variation possibilities of its improvement are wide, and it shows its special possibilities in every class of future teachers and students. So, it becomes clear that the introduction of new initiatives and innovations in education is a process related to the personality of the future teacher and his professional and creative abilities.

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